

ECOLOGY AND NUTRITION IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the solution of such problems as environmental problem and food security in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the salty land of the Aral Sea.

Keywords: environmental problems, food security, food industry, raw materials, Aral Sea, situation, problem solving, methods.

INTRODUCTION

In order to further improve the ecological situation in the Aral Sea of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, to solve problems arising in the field of environmental protection and to ensure that the population lives in a safe environment, comprehensive measures are being consistently implemented. The Aral Sea Region Development Fund under the Ministry of Finance has been established. flora and fauna are being protected and preserved. In this connection, International Food Day is widely celebrated every year on October 16 with a view to eliminating the problem of food shortages among the world's population.

Depending on the location of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 37% (percent) of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a desert zone. To create favorable conditions for the prevention and improvement of public health, quality and standard of living of the population, improving the system of waste management for a long time, as well as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2017 № PF-5024 "In the field of ecology and environment in accordance with the decree many reforms are carried out". "On improving the system of state management" The Republic of Karakalpakstan ranks last in the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of ecological condition and land productivity.

Growth in agricultural production in the

Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2019-2021 was to be provided by expanding the sown area for crops (potatoes by 0.6 thousand hectares in 2017-2021, vegetables by 1.5 thousand hectares, melons by 0.3 thousand hectares, fodder by 5.5 thousand . ha, industrial oilseeds by 4.5 thousand ha, orchards by 0.5 thousand ha, vineyard by 0.5 thousand ha), as well as by increasing the yield of crops (potatoes by 25.2 q/ha, vegetables by 47.5 c/ha, gourds by 14.3 c/ha, fruits by 8.2 c/ha. At the same time, in order to more successfully solve the problems of the development of the agricultural sector in the context of increasing climate change, there is also a need to take measures in the field of legal incentives and regulation at the national level, while providing for: [4:91-100].

Food industry in the Aral Sea can be segmented as follows

Fruit & vegetable processing

Milk & milk products

Fish, poultry, eggs & products
 Meat & meat products
 Bread, biscuits & other bakery products
 Edible oil/fats.[6.421-429].

At present most of the industries are in unorganized sectors. So, number of problems are arising from different sections of the industries. Some of the basic problems encountered by Aral Sea food industries of raw materials at different levels are given below.

The volume of export of horticultural products exceeded 1.4 million tons, increasing by 1.5 barbar compared to 2016. In accordance with the implementation of measures of the Concept of development of organic agriculture and organic food production of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years in the Republic of Uzbekistan implemented large-scale practical reforms: including 7 subsidies for the amount of 975 million soums, the level of implementation - 4.6%, for the remaining types of food products will be allocated subsidies. delivered 749.1 thousand tons.

Summary

Taking into account the above data, it can be concluded that food industry materials are in much better condition in the conditions of the raw Aral Sea. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce new methods of solving problems related to saline lands. This is related to the need of raw materials for industry. This affects not only the economy of the country, but also the way of life of people. In order to further improve environmental climatic conditions and to further improve food security, many strategic reforms are being implemented.

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